

NEST EXIT BEHAVIOR IN *HETEROTRIGONA ITAMA* TO THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND LIGHT FACTORS

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Nest exit activity in stingless bees is an important indicator of colony health and efficient resource collection. Stingless bees are highly dependent on external environmental conditions that determine their activity patterns. One of the main factors that influence this activity is temperature and light intensity. Ambient temperature plays a crucial role in determining how often bees leave the hive to forage. Optimal temperatures, usually between 25°C and 35°C, show high foraging activity. Temperatures that are too low can cause bees to become less active as their bodies require a lot of energy to stay warm, which can reduce the frequency and duration of foraging. However, when the temperature is too high, it can cause dehydration and stress, which also affects hive activity. In addition, temperature also affects bee metabolism. At optimal temperatures, bees' metabolism is at an efficient level, allowing them to fly longer and farther in search of food. Significant changes in temperature, both up and down, can cause metabolic disturbances that impact the efficiency of foraging and nectar and pollen collection. Light is also an important factor in bees' foraging activities. Sunlight provides the energy needed to see and navigate the environment. Bees use daylight to determine time and direction, which are important abilities in finding and returning to the hive after foraging. Sufficient light allows bees to see flowers clearly and recognize colors that attract them to food sources. On the other hand, too low light intensity, such as on a cloudy day or in a dense forest, can reduce the ability of bees to forage effectively as their vision is impaired.

Worker bees are active in the process of finding food at any given time. Food such as pollen, nectar and resin are used to meet the needs of the colony. Stingless bees also play an important role as pollinators in tropical rainforests and pollinate various plants (Herwina et al., 2022). These bees are not only ecologically important, but also produce honey as well as several other products such as wax, royal jelly and propolis (Salamah et al., 2023). The flight activity of worker bees is influenced by food availability, and favorable environmental conditions. In West Sumatra, stingless bees are divided into 2-4 types of bees that actively forage in nature, the most common types include *Heterotrigona itama*, *Geniotrigona thoracica*, and *Tetragonula leaviceps* (Puteri & Herwina, 2022). Based on previous studies, there is a gap regarding environmental factors that affect nest exit activity in *H. itama* that are not fully understood. This study focuses more on other aspects such as the availability of food sources and differences in entrances to stingless bee nests (Gonzalez, 2013). Temperature and light have an important role in the amount of honey production each day. Based on the statement of Nugroho and Soesilohadi (2015), foraging activity in stingless bees can be influenced by several environmental conditions including temperature, light intensity, humidity, and wind speed. Studies examining the influence of temperature and light factors tend to be conducted on other bee species such as *Apis mellifera* (Shaara, 2014). This research is particularly important given that climate change has a major

influence on overall bee behavior patterns (Potts et al., 2010). Previous research has shown that temperature and light are the main factors influencing nest foraging behavior in several bee species. Based on the research of Smith and Brown (2015), it shows that higher light intensity can increase the daily activity of bees. However, these studies mostly focused on other honey bee species and paid less attention to stingless bees such as *H. itama*. Optimal temperature has a major effect on the foraging activity of stingless bees. This is in accordance with Shaara (2014) statement that optimal environmental temperature can increase foraging activity in honey bees, temperatures that are too extreme can reduce the performance of the bees themselves and have an impact on their production needs. The study by Kajobe and Roubik (2016), analyzed that honey bees show significant activity in the morning and evening, but did not explore further the effect of temperature and light. Based on the study by Ahmad et al. (2022) showed that *H. itama*, one of the stingless bee species found in the tropics, is very responsive to changes in temperature and light intensity. Tropical bees have a different response to light fluctuations than bees in temperate regions (Harrison & Roberts, 2012). This research is important because it provides an early picture of how different bee species respond to the same environmental factors.

This study aims to address the knowledge gaps identified in previous studies, especially in the context of knowing the nest entry and exit behavior of *H. itama* species under different temperature and light intensity conditions and obtain a correlation between stingless bee foraging activities and environmental factors. Based on the research of Bosi et al. (2019) this experiment was conducted using a series of temperature and light sensors installed around the beehive. The use of these sensors makes it possible to obtain accurate and real-time data on environmental conditions. The sensors have the ability to record temperature changes to understand how temperature variations affect the frequency and duration of bee activity. Another study by Smith et al. (2020) used temperature sensors placed at several points around the hive and found that temperatures in the range of 25-30°C were the most optimal for hive entry and exit activities. Meanwhile, light sensors are used to measure light intensity in various conditions, from low light in the morning and evening to high light during the day. The lux sensor can be used to record variations in light intensity, with higher light intensity correlating with an increase in nest exit frequency. Activity peaks when sunlight reaches its peak during the day (Gonzalez et al., 2018). This not only increases research efficiency but also allows for a more comprehensive picture of bee behavior patterns under various environmental conditions. The combination of temperature and light data collected with sensors can be used to predict bee behavior and formulate strategies to improve colony health and productivity (Rodriguez et al., 2019). Data will be collected continuously over a period of time to obtain seasonal variations. In addition, surveillance cameras are installed to visually record bee activity, so that data can be analyzed for correlations between changes in temperature and light with the frequency of exiting and entering the hive (Hussain et al., 2017). Under extreme temperature conditions, bees may prefer to stay inside the hive to protect themselves from unfavorable environmental conditions. Regular and high hive exit activity indicates that bees are in favorable environmental conditions, whereas a decrease in this activity may be a sign of environmental stress.

Statistical data analysis is also required to identify consistent behavioral patterns. Correlation analysis can be used to evaluate the individual effects of interacting temperature and light on bee behavior (Gehan et al., 2020). Stingless bees are eusocial species that are strongly influenced by environmental conditions in determining their daily activities. Higher temperatures tend to increase activity because bees are more active in foraging and performing other colony tasks at optimal temperature conditions. Conversely, temperatures that are too low can reduce their activity due to discomfort that risks death. The light factor is used by bees as navigation and orientation when foraging outside the hive. This is in accordance with the statement of Silva et al. (2021) showing that there is a significant positive correlation between light intensity and frequency of nest entry and exit, with peak activity occurring in the morning and afternoon when sunlight is strongest. Based on other research by Goncalves et al. (2019) indicates that temperature and light are related factors, they have an independent influence on bee behavior. Sudden temperature fluctuations or abrupt changes in light intensity can disrupt bee activity patterns, suggesting that environmental stability is also an important factor. *H. itama* also show behavioral adaptations to daily temperature fluctuations. For example, in the morning when temperatures are still cool, bees tend to leave the hive less and begin to increase their activity as temperatures rise throughout the day. Temperature and light intensity are inversely related to humidity. If temperature and light intensity rise, air humidity tends to fall (Gresia, 2021). This activity peaks at the most favorable temperature and then decreases again when the temperature is too hot during the day. This activity pattern suggests a close relationship between temperature and foraging activity in *H. itama*.

Research on the nest exit behavior of *H. itama* under the influence of temperature and light factors shows how important these two environmental elements are in determining the daily activities of stingless bees. The results revealed that *H. itama*, a stingless bee species found in the tropics, is highly responsive to changes in temperature and light intensity. At optimal temperatures between 25-30°C, the bees showed a significant increase in nest entry and exit activity, reflecting the thermal comfort and efficiency that allows them to perform essential tasks such as foraging and colony care. When the temperature dropped below or rose above this range, their activity decreased dramatically, suggesting that temperature extremes can hinder their mobility and performance. Overall, this study confirms that proper management of temperature and light is crucial in conservation and beekeeping practices for *H. itama*. By maintaining the environment at optimal temperatures and ensuring adequate light availability, beekeepers can improve the health and productivity of their colonies. This research also provides valuable insights for conservation efforts of stingless bees, which are important pollinators in ecosystems.

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